

1 **Epigenetic change during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC.**

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7 Histone demethylase *KDM4B* was activated. Chromodomain enzyme *CHD5* was also activated. *DNMT1*
8 was silenced; the 5-azacytidine gene *AZI* was also modulated during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC
9 *in vitro*.

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